

Bishnoi

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Hinduism

Bishnoi

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Bishnoi Communities in India

Region tags: Asia, South Asia, India, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Odisha

This map focuses on the concentration of the Bishnoi population, which is mostly in the western portion of the Indian state of Rajasthan. Rajasthan is outlined as the outer polygon, while the western reaches of the state where Bishnoi communities are at their highest concentration, are the inner polygon. Smaller polygons also represent concentrations of Bishnoi in Odisha state, Madhya Pradesh and in the vicinity of New Delhi.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Jain, Pankaj. *Dharma and Ecology of Hindu Communities: Sustenance and Sustainability*. Routledge, 2011

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://edugreen.teri.res.in/explore/forestry/bisnoi.htm>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <http://edugreen.teri.res.in/explore/forestry/bisnoi.htm>

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1000000

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):
– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by class:
– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:
– No

↳ Assigned by gender:
– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:
– Yes

↳ Assigned by some other factor:
– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 80

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):
– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by class:
– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:
– No

↳ Assigned by gender:
– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:
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↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

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Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1000000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 80

Scripture

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Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

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– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

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↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.
Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans’ behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Field doesn't know

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– Yes

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
– Yes

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

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Reincarnation in this world:

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Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

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– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
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- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
– Yes

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 10000

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

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Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

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Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

– No

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– I don't know

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– I don't know

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– I don't know

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– I don't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– I don't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– I don't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

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↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– I don't know

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Bishnoi, Jain, Pankaj. *Dharma and Ecology of Hindu Communities*. Routledge, 2016.
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